

Request for Information: Toward a standardized data framework for plant cell and tissue culture

Purpose

Plants are the backbone of our food system and a foundational source of medicines, materials, and ecological stability. As our understanding of plant biology has deepened, we've begun to recognize their potential for alternative applications—from producing biofuels and enabling gigaton-scale carbon capture to extracting critical metals through phytomining. Yet, realizing this potential often depends on our ability to manipulate and regenerate plants effectively in controlled environments.

In plant tissue culture (PTC), non-reproductive (somatic) cells can be induced to proliferate into a mass of dedifferentiated cells (callus) or follow developmental pathways that regenerate specific organs or entire plants. As a result, PTC's broad applicability underpins efforts in genetic engineering, plant conservation, metabolite production, *in vitro* selection of stress-resistant food crop variants, and commercial horticulture. While regeneration using PTC is powerful, it's constrained by hormonal complexity, low efficiency, high labor costs, and genotype dependence—regeneration can vary widely between species. Although totipotency is a theoretically shared trait among plants, in practice, regeneration outcomes remain inconsistent and difficult to predict. Broad regeneration patterns are obscured by isolated studies that track outcomes only at the genus-, species-, or cultivar-level. This begs the question: could a standardized, open dataset capturing PTC outcomes across a wider phylogenetic and experimental spectrum reveal biological patterns and reduce the reliance on trial-and-error?

Figure 1: Two applications of plant tissue culture. Transgenic plants can be generated by introducing transgenes into aggregated, dedifferentiated cells (callus) via *Agrobacterium*. The transformed cells are regenerated into whole plants, using plant growth regulators to promote shoot and root development. Transgenic plantlets (T_0) are then acclimated to soil and backcrossed with elite breeding lines (BC_1) to combine desirable agronomic traits with the transgene. Micropropagation is a technique used to produce large numbers of genetically identical plants from small amounts of starting tissue. It is widely used for plant conservation, commercial horticulture, and disease elimination by isolating and culturing meristematic tissue.

Recognizing the likelihood that phylogenetic patterns are connected to outcomes *in vitro*, efforts to aggregate PTC data have been made since the early 2000s.^{1,2} However, these efforts tend to be limited to search-based functionalities—locating and returning relevant data from a larger dataset generated by mining PTC literature. Advancements in machine learning and genome sequencing now allow us to progress from search to prediction. This opens the door to uncovering patterns across taxa linked to regeneration success, predicting optimal *in vitro* conditions faster, and identifying putative genes that impact *in vitro* morphogenesis and embryonic potential such as WUSCHEL (WUS) and BABY BOOM (BBM).^{3,4,5} Still, three major bottlenecks prevent the development of predictive PTC models:

1. Standardized data and metadata frameworks have not been widely adopted, limiting PTC data interoperability.
2. Negative data is not shared, yet it is essential for eliminating false positives and enabling uncertainty modeling (e.g. this set of conditions has a 30% chance of leading to an embryogenic callus).
3. Existing PTC data is likely phylogenetically biased—clustering around agricultural, medicinal, and model species. Thus, species that may be of interest for biofuel production, carbon sequestration, conservation, phytomining, or other purposes may have little to no information available on regeneration techniques.

This project aims to address these gaps by first developing PTC metadata standards and later testing and refining these standards with a limited scope of species and experimental conditions. To reveal phylogenetic patterns and putative genomic signatures associated with *in vitro* outcomes, genomic data and time-lapse image data with [EcoFABs](#)—autoclavable plant growth chambers designed for controlled studies—will be collected.^{6,7} Depending on the results of the proof-of-concept dataset and community feedback, other data types may be considered (e.g. LC-MS/MS for nutrient or hormone uptake, RNA-seq, etc.).

Figure 2: Proposed workflow to establish standardized PTC metadata schema and an open dataset.

¹ Herring A, Lineberger RD. (1995). The Plant Tissue Culture Information Exchange Media. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTSCI.35.3.450E>

² Cincinnati Zoo and Botanical Garden (2025). Comparative In Vitro (CIV) Database. <https://cincinnatizoo.org/exceptional-plant-conservation-network/tools-for-exceptional-plant-in-vitro-research/comparative-in-vitro-civ-database/>

³ Laux T, Mayer KFX, Berger J, Jürgens G. (1996). The WUSCHEL gene is required for shoot and floral meristem integrity in *Arabidopsis*. <http://doi.org/10.1242/dev.122.1.87>

⁴ Boutillier K et al. (2002). Ectopic Expression of BABY BOOM Triggers a Conversion from Vegetative to Embryonic Growth. <https://doi.org/10.1105/tpc.001941>

⁵ Lowe et al. (2016). Morphogenic Regulators Baby boom and Wuschel Improve Monocot Transformation. <https://doi.org/10.1105/tpc.16.00124>

⁶ Zengler et al. (2019). EcoFABs: advancing microbiome science through standardized fabricated ecosystems. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0465-0>

⁷ Novak, V. (2024). Use of EcoFAB 2.0 for reproducible plant-microbe interaction experiments. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kxygxydkl8j/v1>

Data generation is most impactful when users help shape how that data is captured from the start. This RFI seeks to better understand which data types would be most valuable for machine learning models currently in development, as well as the range of predictive use cases that a diverse plant tissue culture (PTC) dataset could support. You're welcome to answer as many or as few questions as you choose. Please note that while we aim to align data collection with community needs where feasible, submitting a response does not guarantee that specific feedback will be incorporated.

Requested Information

1. What are your primary applications of plant tissue culture? Regeneration post genetic transformation? Cell lines for metabolite production? *In vitro* selection of stress-resistant variants? Micropropagation? Other?
2. Which species or taxa would you like to see represented in a proof-of-concept dataset? Provide a list of up to 10 species or taxa, ranked from highest to lowest priority. If applicable, indicate specific cultivars or varieties of interest and conservation status rankings.
3. What morphological considerations should be taken into account when evaluating cell survival, callus development, rooting, and shooting? E.g. Leaf color discoloration could suggest nutrient deficiency or callus color could distinguish between embryogenic vs. non-embryogenic calli.
4. For those interested in *in vitro* selection under stress, which traits are high priority for you and how do you prefer to measure them (e.g. drought tolerance or osmotic stress with PEG-6000 or mannitol or salinity tolerance with NaCl)?
5. For those actively building machine learning models that may use this dataset, what specific data types would be ideal for your models? Feel free to specify down to machine and file formats (e.g. PacBio HiFi, segmented and cropped image data in ome-zarr format, etc.)?
6. What discoveries or capabilities would make a plant tissue culture dataset obsolete (e.g. the ability to reliably transform seeds, pollen, or meristems across species)?
7. Are you willing to join a small working group of data users as we develop and refine our approach?
8. Would you like to participate in the proof-of-concept dataset collection? Note: Independent researchers and labs are open to participate, but they must have access to the proper materials and equipment needed to execute the experiments. Notable pieces of equipment include a laminar flow hood, a plant growth chamber, and a Photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) meter.

Responses to this RFI should be no more than 2 pages in length and submitted in PDF format to Jasmine Neal at jasbneal@gmail.com by June 30, 2025. We look forward to working with you!